

WP 2220 - SI-traceable system development

Report on the field campaign for the validation of solar & lunar spectral irradiance measurements with the Solar/Lunar PFR.

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Campaign overview

A 3-week field campaign for the validation of the SI-traceable measurements of solar and lunar irradiance against the standard Langley extrapolation calibration and the existing of the top-of-the-atmosphere (TOA) solar (Gröbner, Kröger et al. 2017, Coddington, Richard et al. 2023) and lunar (Kieffer and Stone 2005, Barreto, Román et al. 2019, Toledano, Taylor et al. 2023) irradiance was organized at the Izaña observatory at Tenerife, Canary islands, (28.3°N, 16.5°E, 2.4 km) in the frame work of the EMPIR 19ENV04 MAPP project (3 - 23 September 2022).

The high-altitude Observatory at Izaña, is ideally suited for retrieving ToA solar spectra using the Langley-plot technique due to the high frequency of pristine and stable atmosphere above the station.

Several SI-calibrated filter- and spectro-radiometers have participated. The participating filterradiometers were the Precision solar (PFR-98-N-001) and lunar FilterRadiometers (PFR-98-L-002), the master Cimel instruments #1270, #917 and Prede-POM. Direct spectral irradiance measurements were performed by 4 spectroradiometers: QASUME (300 to 550 nm), QASUME-IR (550 to 1700 nm), BTS (300 to 2150 nm) and Precision Solar Spectroradiometer, PSR#009 (316 to 1030 nm).

Solar irradiance

In the duration of the campaign 7 days were favourable for determining the ToA irradiance with the Langley method. The aerosol optical depth (AOD) and the solar irradiance measured with the PFR is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Solar irradiance and AOD at 500 nm measured by the PFR-N-001 at the Izaña observatory (28.3° N, 16.5° W, 2.4 km) during the MAPP project campaign 3 - 23 September 2022.

Precision FilterRadiometer (PFR-98-N-001)

The PFR-98-N-001 is equipped with four independent narrow spectral channels centred at 368 nm, 412 nm, 500 nm, and 862 nm. The interference filters have a full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) of 4 nm to 5 nm and an optical density of 6 for out-of-band transmittance.

The PFR-98-N-001 has been calibrated at the TUnable Lasers In Photometry (TULIP) facility of the Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt (PTB), Braunschweig, Germany in January-February 2021 (Kouremeti, Nevas et al. 2022). The stability of the instrument has been monitored through comparison to the GAWPFR-TRIAD (Kazadzis, Kouremeti et al. 2018a). The performed Langley’s showed an agreement to the within 0.3% to the initial calibration (Table 1).

The SI ToA retrieval was compared to the GAWPFR-TRIAD and Langley calibration and the agreement was within the combined expanded uncertainty of the calibration procedures and the ToA spectral uncertainties, verifying the results from the Davos comparison (Kouremeti, Nevas et al. 2022).

Table 1: PFR ToA values from calibration against the GAWPFR-Triad and Langley calibration during the campaign.

Wavelength (nm)	862	500	412	368
ToA PFR-TRIAD (V)	3.380	3.717	3.503	4.011
ToA Langley (V)	3.376	3.712	3.493	4.006
Difference	0.1%	0.1%	0.3%	0.1%

Table 2: PFR ToA values from convolved ToA SI-traceable spectra TSIS-1 HSRS and QASUMEFTS with the spectral responsivity of the PFR determined at PTB. Comparison to the calibrations based on GAWPFRTriad and in-situ Langley.

	TSIS-1 HSRS				QASUMEFTS	
Wavelength (nm)	862	500	412	368	412	368
ToA convolved with PTB calibration (V)	3.360	3.733	3.525	4.007	3.537	4.044
Differences of PTB and ToA to relative calibration						
PFR-TRIAD	0.59%	-0.42%	-0.62%	0.09%	-0.96%	0.09%
Langley	0.47%	-0.55%	-0.90%	-0.04%	-1.24%	-0.04%

Lunar irradiance

Precision FilterRadiometer (PFR-98-L-002)

The PFR-98-L-002 is equipped with four independent narrow spectral channels centred at 412 nm, 500 nm, 675 nm, and 862 nm. The interference filters have a full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) of 4 nm to 5 nm and an optical density of 6 for out-of-band transmittance. The Lunar-PFR PFR-98-L-002 Lunar was calibrated in November 2021 at PTB following the same procedure as the Sun-PFR , PFR-98-N-001 (Kouremeti, Nevas et al. 2022).

The lunar irradiance measurements at the 4 PFR channels for the Sep.2022 lunar cycle is shown in Figure 3. Seven Langley extrapolations were possible, with stable atmospheric conditions verified by the daytime AOD measurements covering lunar phases ranging from 6° to 58°.

Figure 2: Lunar irradiance measurements at the 4 PFR channels performed at the Izaña observatory (28.3° N, 16.5° W, 2.4 km) during the MAPP project campaign 3 - 23 September 2022.

In the case of lunar Langley, the phase dependency of the irradiance has to be accounted for. This approach relies on the phase dependency given by the lunar irradiance models according to the equation:

$$\ln \left(\frac{I_{PFR}(\lambda_c, t)}{I_{ToA}(\lambda_c, t)} \right) + \tau_{ray}(\lambda_c)m + \tau_{O_3}(\lambda_c)m_{O_3} = -m\tau_{aod}(\lambda_c)$$

Where $I_{PFR}(\lambda_c, t)$ the lunar irradiance measured by the PFR, $I_{ToA}(\lambda_c, t)$ the lunar irradiance given by the model at the centroid wavelength λ_c and time t . The extinction of the irradiances due to Rayleigh scattering (τ_{ray}) (Bodhaine, Wood et al. 1999) and ozone absorption (τ_{O_3}), are calculated based on the and the ozone cross section by Serdyuchenko, Gorshchev et al. (2014) and ozone concentration measured given by interpolation of daily values of OMI overpass ([aura_omi_l2ovp_omto3_v8.5](#)). The optical path in the atmosphere, airmass, of ozone (m_{O_3}) assuming of ozone layer height at 30 km. τ_{aod} and m the aerosol optical depth and airmass.

The lunar irradiance models used are

- ROLO (Kieffer and Stone 2005) – accounting for the spectral responsivity of the PFR
 - ROLO – TSIS-1 adjustment
 - ROLO* TSIS-1 and air-LUSI adjustment (August 2023; Woodward et al. 2022)
- RIMO (Barreto, Román et al. 2019) and
- LIME (Toledano, Taylor et al. 2023) models.

An example for 5 nights of the performance of the of Langley with respect to nighttime and daytime AOD at 862 nm is shown in Figure 3 for the three models. Using the Langley of the night the AOD agreement is very close to the interpolated daytime AOD of the Langley calibrated PFR-N-001 and SI-AOD (PFR-N-001 & TSIS) verifying the validity of the ToA retrieval.

Figure 3: Nighttime AOD at 862 nm based on the same night Langley calibration for the 3 lunar irradiance models ROLO, RIMO, and LIME.

The ToA retrievals indicate the deviation of each model and to the PFR ToA. A detailed uncertainty budget has been performed for each Langley accounting for the uncertainty of the calibration, noise in the measurements, field of view inhomogeneity, Langley residuals, uncertainties due airmass, refraction correction, ozone, and pressure. The deviation of the lunar irradiance models and the PFR retrievals are shown in Figure 4 (bar) and the errorbars indicate the combined expanded relative uncertainty of the PFR ToA irradiance including the variability observed over the lunar cycle, as expanded standard deviation of the 7 Langley's ($k=2$).

The ROLO* shows the best compatibility with the PFR retrievals with the 862 nm to be better than 1% which is the requested limit for accurate AOD using the SI-traceable approach. The rest of the wavelengths are within 2.5% and 4%. The LIME model for the wavelengths 500 nm – 862 nm are between 4% and 7%. Higher deviations are observed for ROLO-TSIS and RIMO. The minimum standard deviation over the cycle is for the ROLO in the range of 0.5% and 0.9%, comparable with the combined expanded relative uncertainty of the PFR lunar irradiance (Figure 5). In general, all models predict the lunar irradiance phase dependency within 1% (with slightly higher uncertainty at 675 nm), while the offsets are the limiting factor for an SI-traceable nighttime AOD retrieval.

Figure 4: Comparison of the PFR-L Top-of-Atmosphere lunar irradiance to the lunar irradiance models. The errorbars indicate the combined expanded uncertainty of the PFR-L retrieval over the lunar cycle

Figure 5: Uncertainty components of the ToA retrievals and comparison to the lunar irradiance models for the 7 days with lunar phases ranging from 6° to 58°.

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